

PHOTOBIMODULATION IN RESTORATIVE DENTISTRY AND ENDODONTICS

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ABSTRACT

Photobiomodulation (PBM), also known as low-level laser therapy (LLLT), is a noninvasive treatment that uses specific wavelengths of red and infrared light to induce various physiological effects in cells and tissues. This light-based therapy initiates photochemical reactions within cells, leading to the production of molecules such as adenosine triphosphate (ATP), reactive oxygen species (ROS), and calcium ions. These molecules play a crucial role in promoting cell proliferation, differentiation, and migration. PBM has been shown to reduce pain, stimulate tissue healing, and exert anti-inflammatory effects on targeted tissues. Research into PBM began in the 1960s, and numerous studies over the years have demonstrated its wide-ranging applications across different areas of dentistry. Even today, ongoing research aims to uncover additional therapeutic benefits of this modality. In dentistry, PBM is used to treat a variety of oral conditions such as aphthous ulcers, herpes lesions, pemphigus, and burning mouth syndrome. It also helps in alleviating pain after orthodontic procedures, managing temporomandibular joint disorders (TMDs), and enhancing local anesthesia effectiveness. Additionally, PBM proves valuable in addressing general dental pain and continues to show promise in various clinical applications.

Introduction

The acronym LASER stands for Light Amplification by Stimulated Emission of Radiation. It was first developed by Maiman on July 7, 1960, at Hughes Research Laboratories in Malibu, California. Maiman achieved this using a combination of helium and neon gases. Over time, numerous researchers explored this subject, revealing the wide-ranging applications of lasers across different fields of study. It was determined that the introduction of lasers to dentistry was helpful to dental practise. CO₂, Nd:YAG, and Er:YAG lasers can be used effectively on

both soft and hard tissues. Hard lasers have a number of disadvantages, including heat injury to the pulp of the tooth and a high price. Additionally, soft lasers or cool lasers are based on low-cost semiconductor diode diodes. They are also commonly referred to as low-level laser treatment (LLLT) or biostimulation.¹ Lasers are increasingly employed in dentistry, revolutionizing both oral health care practices and improving patients' quality of life by efficiently performing a wide range of dental procedures.²

Charles Townes and his colleagues established the laser era by introducing microwave amplification by stimulated emission of radiation (MASER) in 1954 and 1955 in physics review articles. Despite the fact that multiple experts informed Townes that his device would not function, others began creating variants of his technology, and in 1960, the first light-emitting MASER was produced, which later became known as the LASER.

Consequently, numerous clinical and laboratory studies have been conducted to explore the physiological effects and therapeutic benefits of Low-Level Laser Therapy (LLLT). According to the North American Association for Laser Therapy, LLLT involves applying non-thermal laser light, using photons from the visible and infrared spectra, to promote tissue healing and pain management. Beyond lasers, research found that non-coherent light sources like light-emitting diodes (LEDs) also possess biostimulatory properties, leading to the classification of "low-dose light therapies." The term "Photobiomodulation" (PBM) accurately describes these low-power treatments, encompassing a wide range of electromagnetic wavelengths that can stimulate or inhibit biological processes in target tissues, with therapeutic implications. Laser therapy operates by delivering energy to trigger biological responses. According to Arndt-Schultz's Law of Biostimulation, low-dose energy enhances biological processes, resulting in various physiological changes in cells and tissues. This non-invasive treatment effectively relieves pain, reduces inflammation, and supports tissue repair and regeneration.

Photobiomodulation (PBM) utilizes electromagnetic radiation within visible wavelengths (380–700 nm) or near-infrared wavelengths (700–1010 nm), which are minimally absorbed by water and penetrate soft and hard tissues to depths of 3–15 mm, respectively. PBM functions by activating photoreceptors and enhancing adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production. This stimulation of ATP production boosts cellular activity through the Krebs cycle. This review aims to explore various types of lasers, the mechanisms involved, and the PBM treatment protocols used in Endodontic and Restorative dentistry.

Discussion

Types of lasers

There are two types of lasers: (i) High intensity and (ii) Low intensity.

- 1) Warm lasers operate at high intensities with wavelengths ranging from 450 to 532 nm in the visible spectrum and 800 to 2940 nm in the infrared spectrum. They are specifically engineered for performing surgical procedures on both hard and soft tissues.³
- 2) Low-intensity cold lasers, also referred to as PBM treatment, employ low-power radiation. These lasers exert non-thermal effects on tissues, promoting tissue repair, reducing inflammation, and alleviating pain. Mester et al. were the first to publish findings on LLLT in the medical literature.⁴

PBM treatment harnesses the therapeutic effects of specific wavelengths of red or near-infrared light, inducing various physiological changes in cells and tissues. This non-invasive therapy effectively reduces pain, inflammation, and supports tissue repair and regeneration.

Mechanism of action

Photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) utilizes non-ionizing light sources such as LEDs, lasers, and broad-spectrum light that emit visible and near-infrared wavelengths. Recent research has focused on elucidating the effects of PBM on cellular processes. The underlying mechanism of PBM involves interaction with cells at a photochemical level, stimulating mitochondria which harbor chromophores capable of absorbing photons from PBM. Key to this process is the enzyme Cytochrome c oxidase (Cco), which modulates various substances including Adenosine triphosphate (ATP), nitric oxide (NO), reactive oxygen species (ROS), and calcium ions.⁵

According to reports, the PBM can affect cellular activity in four distinct ways.⁶ (1) After light is absorbed by Cco, it accelerates the rate of electron transfer in the respiratory chain, leading to an increase in ATP production. (2) Cco enzymatically converts NO₂ to NO and reduces O₂ to H₂O. NO exerts an antagonistic effect by binding to Cco, thereby inhibiting respiration and reducing ATP production. PBM could potentially disrupt the interaction between NO and Cco, leading to elevated levels of free NO and subsequent effects

such as hypoxia and immunological signaling.(3) PBM suppresses the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS). This antioxidative effect is beneficial in stressed and injured cells. Despite its role in cell signaling and maintaining homeostasis, ROS generation is reduced under PBM therapy. (4) Some of the energy is transformed into heat, creating a photothermal effect that permeates tissues. Exposure of cells to near-infrared light activates light-sensitive ion channels, triggering an influx of calcium ions which interact with ROS and cAMP. According to Wang et al., blue and green light of shorter wavelengths activate light-gated ion channels, including rhodopsin channels and other chromophores. These mechanisms collectively enhance cellular proliferation, differentiation, and migration.⁷

Uses of photobiomodulation in restorative dentistry and endodontic

1) Direct pulp capping

PBMT is applied in direct pulp capping (DPC) procedures for its notable advantages in reducing inflammation and discomfort, accelerating wound healing, and promoting the formation of robust dentin tissue. Despite the significant influence of technique and materials used in DPC observed in animal and in vitro studies, clinical trials have yielded inconclusive results regarding the effectiveness of PBMT. Additional clinical research is needed to establish definitive conclusions.^{8,9,10}

2) Dentinal hypersensitivity

Dentinal hypersensitivity (DH) is characterized by persistent pain in dentistry, often difficult to predict accurately. External stimuli such as temperature changes or chemicals activate A-delta nerve fibers within dentinal tubules, causing sharp tooth pain. Over the years, several treatment approaches for DH have been explored.^{11,12} Matsumoto et al. pioneered the use of laser technology in the mid-1980s for treating dentin hypersensitivity. Currently, photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) is recognized as a crucial non-drug, non-invasive treatment option.¹³

Various lasers have been extensively researched and evaluated for treating dentinal hypersensitivity (DH). These lasers operate through two primary mechanisms: first, high-power laser treatments can close off dentinal tubules, while also modifying nerve endings to

influence pain thresholds; second, they stimulate the production of reactive dentine.^{14,15} Clinical studies have demonstrated that lasers such as GaAlAs (795 or 830 nm) or InGaAlP (660 nm), when used with specific radiation protocols—typically involving power settings ranging from 15 to 120 mW, energy densities of 1.8 to 10 J/cm², durations of 24 to 160 seconds per session, administered over 3 to 6 sessions, in continuous mode with a scanning motion—can significantly alleviate dentin sensitivity.

Due to the subjective nature of dentinal hypersensitivity (DH), there remains considerable debate regarding the effectiveness of treatments, despite numerous studies demonstrating their efficacy. Various protocols for photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) have been explored in clinical research to address this non-invasively. Lasers can achieve desensitization by either sealing dentinal tubules through high-power treatments or influencing the nervous system to promote the formation of secondary dentin. Optimal relief from hypersensitive dentin often involves initial pain management with laser therapy followed by the application of chemical agents. Marsilo et al. found that their DH treatment approach achieved a statistically significant success rate of 88.8% compared to controls, a distinction that persisted even 60 days after treatment.¹⁶

3) Teeth bleaching

The primary concern with teeth whitening, especially through in-office methods, is dental hypersensitivity.¹⁷ Following bleaching procedures, between 55% to 100% of patients typically report increased tooth sensitivity.¹⁸ Photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) emerges as a non-drug, non-invasive approach to alleviate post-treatment sensitivity.¹⁹ Most research in this field has focused on laboratory settings, examining PBMT's impact on odontoblastic cell responses and its ability to neutralize by-products from bleaching gels.²⁰ Clinical studies have demonstrated that applying PBMT with specific diode laser parameters (780, 810 nm), ranging from 70 to 200 mW, for 10 to 15 seconds at an energy density of 12 J/cm², effectively reduces tooth sensitivity following in-office bleaching. Despite PBMT's success in mitigating clinical sensitivity and neutralizing bleaching gel cytotoxicity, current research findings from in vivo and in vitro studies do not fully elucidate PBMT's mechanisms, highlighting the need for further clinical investigation.

4) Postoperative sensitivity in restorations

One common issue following composite restorative procedures is dental sensitivity, often attributed to polymerization shrinkage. Despite various proposed remedies to mitigate this issue, the optimal approach is still under active investigation. Recent studies have explored the use of low-power lasers to reduce postoperative sensitivity, especially in deep restorations. Moosavi et al. recommended photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) for deep cavities, advocating their specific protocol using a 630 nm laser at 28 mW in continuous wave mode for 60 seconds, delivering 1.68 J of energy. They observed significant reduction in postoperative sensitivity in class V composite restorations with this approach.^{21,22,23}

5) Postoperative pain after endodontic treatment

Pain is a commonly encountered side effect of endodontic procedures, significantly affecting an individual's quality of life. Thermal, chemical, or microbiological factors can lead to pulp tissue damage, contributing to discomfort.²⁴ Studies indicate a higher incidence of pain following root canal retreatment.²⁵ Low-power laser therapy has garnered significant attention as a pain relief technique, supported by valuable existing research. This non-invasive, cost-effective method offers minimal adverse effects, making it advantageous in clinical practice.²⁶

Yildiz et al.'s study represents a significant investigation into the impact of photobiomodulation therapy (PBM) on postoperative pain in patients with symptomatic apical periodontitis. They employed a 970–15 nm laser with a 200- μ m optical fiber and a bleaching tip positioned 10 mm from the apex tissue, delivering pulses at 0.5 W and 10 Hz. Their findings showed a notable reduction in pain after 30 seconds of PBMT following endodontic treatment. In a separate study, Asnaashari et al. utilized a low-power 808-nm laser with 100 mW power and a 600- μ m fiber diameter, administering a dosage of 70 J/cm² over 80 seconds. Pain intensity was assessed using a visual analogue scale before therapy, immediately post-treatment, and at 4, 8, 12, 24, and 48 hours post-treatment. Results indicated no significant difference in pain levels between the laser-treated group and the control group at any time point, with both groups experiencing pain relief for up to 48 hours. The researchers concluded that PBMT had limited effectiveness in reducing discomfort associated with root canal retreatment in first and second molars.²⁴

Studies suggest that photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) delays the onset of pain, reduces its intensity, and shortens its duration by enhancing the production of chemokines.²⁷ PBMT also suppresses the release of inflammatory factors and pain-related neurotransmitters. Based on these mechanisms, PBMT is hypothesized to be effective in alleviating pain during root canal retreatment. However, due to the limited number of clinical investigations, establishing a precise methodology is currently challenging, highlighting the need for further research in this area.^{28,29}

6) Endodontic surgery

Three clinical studies have investigated the effectiveness of using PBMT in endodontic surgery to reduce pain, swelling, and promote recovery of soft and hard tissues. Lasers with wavelengths of 680 or 810 nm, power outputs ranging from 50 to 75 or 129 mW, energy densities from 3 to 7.5 J/cm², and irradiation times of 360 to 600 seconds (typically 300 seconds) with scanning movements over a 9 to 10 cm² area were utilized intraoperatively and up to 7 days post-surgery.³⁰ Laser treatment has demonstrated beneficial effects on both soft and hard tissue healing and pain management. However, further clinical research is necessary to clarify and expand upon these findings.³¹

7) Regenerative endodontic procedures

Photobiomodulation (PBM) therapy has shown to enhance stem cell differentiation in laboratory settings and promote regeneration of pulp-like tissue in animal studies, leading to increased tertiary dentin formation and improved development of pulp-like tissue. However, slight variations in dosage, application time, and frequency can sometimes lead to minimal effects or even hinder the desired outcomes. Both 660 nm and 810 nm wavelengths have demonstrated promising results in this regard. Nevertheless, other characteristics of PBMT have shown considerable variability across studies. *In vivo* experiments have utilized PBMT with power outputs ranging from 20 to 300 mW and exposure durations ranging from 7 to 300 seconds. Such wide-ranging parameters in scientific literature make it challenging to assess and compare results effectively.

When evaluating cell differentiation rates, all studies consistently found that PBMT yielded beneficial outcomes. However, this was not the case for proliferation or cell viability

rates, as two investigations did not observe an increase in these measures. This discrepancy may be attributed to PBMT's effectiveness being more pronounced under conditions of cellular stress. Factors such as dietary deficiencies or reduced fetal bovine serum in cell culture medium supplementation can induce such stress. Ferreira et al. observed enhanced proliferation rates in cells exposed to 5 J/cm² radiation under stress conditions. In contrast, two studies did not show improved outcomes, potentially due to insufficient stress induction or inadequate PBMT settings to compensate for cellular deficits when using scaffolds or in inflamed pulp contexts.

Conversely, all in vivo studies consistently demonstrated favorable effects of PBMT on dentin-pulp tissue formation, irrespective of the animal species studied. Investigations reporting increased tertiary dentin formation provided measurable data showing that PBMT could enhance dentinogenesis rates, particularly with the use of the 810 nm wavelength in both experiments. Moreira et al.'s study focused on dental pulp regeneration, offering qualitative insights into the properties of newly formed tissue, despite limited quantitative data.³²

Conclusion

Photobiomodulation therapy (PBMT) serves as an alternative to analgesics and anti-inflammatory drugs in dentistry. Its applications encompass postoperative endodontic pain management, endodontic surgery, regenerative endodontics, local anesthesia depth, direct pulp capping, and treatment of tooth hypersensitivity. Multiple studies have provided compelling data supporting the promising role of PBMT in dentistry, demonstrating its effectiveness across various procedures. PBMT's ability to alleviate pain and enhance healing contributes significantly to its growing use in clinical settings. It benefits oral health by promoting tissue repair, reducing inflammation through physiological mechanisms, and enhancing cell migration, proliferation, and differentiation. Optimal outcomes with PBMT depend on factors such as treatment site, anatomical variations, individual patient characteristics, and clinical conditions at the site. Achieving these outcomes requires precise understanding and administration of appropriate dosage, a factor that ongoing research continues to refine. Importantly, PBMT has demonstrated safety in clinical use, further endorsing its integration into dental practice without reported adverse effects.

Reference

1. Carroll JD, Milward MR, Cooper PR, Hadis M, Palin WM. Developments in low level light therapy (LLLT) for dentistry. *Dent Mater.* 2014;30(5):465–75.
2. Kathuria V, Dhillon JK, Kalra G. Low Level Laser Therapy: A Panacea for oral maladies. *Laser Ther.* 2015;24(3):215–23
3. Reza B, Soheil N, Ehsan B, Kouros S, Reza F. Efficacy of photo bio-modulation therapy for pain relief and soft tissue wound healing after dental implant surgery: A double-blind randomized clinical trial. *J Photochemistry Photobiology.* 2021;8:100062.
4. Heiskanen V, Hamblin MR. Photobiomodulation: lasers vs. light emitting diodes? *Photochem Photobiol Sci.* 2018;17:1003–17.
5. Cronshaw M, Parker S, Anagnostaki E, Mylona V, Lynch E, Grootveld M, et al. Photobiomodulation Dose Parameters in Dentistry: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Dent J (Basel).* 2020;8(4):114.
6. Courtois E, Bouleftour W, Guy JB, Louati S, Bensadoun RJ, Rodriguez-Lafrasse C, et al. Mechanisms of PhotoBioModulation (PBM) focused on oral mucositis prevention and treatment: a scoping review. *BMC Oral Health.* 2021;21:220.
7. Wang Y, Huang YY, Wang Y, Lyu P, Hamblin MR. Photobiomodulation (blue and green light) encourages osteoblastic differentiation of human adipose-derived stem cells: role of intracellular calcium and light-gated ion channels. *Sci Rep.* 2016;6:33719.
8. Bidar M, Moushekhian S, Gharechahi M, Talati A, Ahrari F, Bojarpour M, et al. The Effect of Low Level Laser Therapy on Direct Pulp Capping in Dogs. *J Lasers Med Sci.* 2016;7(3):177–83.
9. Shigetani Y, Sasa N, Suzuki H, Okiji T, Ohshima H. GaAlAs Laser Irradiation Induces Active Tertiary Dentin Formation after Pulpal Apoptosis and Cell Proliferation in Rat Molars. *J Endod.* 2011;37(8):1086–91.
10. Ferriello V, Faria MR, Cavalcanti BN. The effects of low-level diode laser treatment and dental pulp-capping materials on the proliferation of L-929 fibroblasts. *J Oral Sci.* 2010;52(1):33–8.
11. Asnaashari M, Moeini M. Effectiveness of lasers in the treatment of dentin hypersensitivity. *J Lasers Med Sci.* 2013;4(1):1–7.

12. Moraschini V, Costa LSD, Go S. Effectiveness for dentin hypersensitivity treatment of non-carious cervical lesions: a meta-analysis. *Clinical Oral Investig.* 2018;22(2):617–31.
13. Sato T, Matsumoto T, Yoshitake K. Clinical application in oral surgery and basic researches of Nd-YAG laser with handpieces designed for dentistry. *J Japan Soc Laser Surg Med.* 1985;5(3):405–8.
14. Gholami GA, Fekrazad R, Esmail-Nejad A, Kalhori KAM. An Evaluation of the Occluding Effects of Er. *Photomed Laser Surg.* 2011;29(2):115–21.
15. Aranha ACC, de Paula Eduardo C, Eduardo C. Effects of Er:YAG and Er,Cr:YSGG lasers on dentine hypersensitivity. Short-term clinical evaluation. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2012;27(4):813–8.
16. Marsilio AL, Rodrigues JR, Borges AB. Effect of the Clinical Application of the GaAlAs Laser in the Treatment of Dentine Hypersensitivity. *J Clin Laser Med Surg.* 2003;21(5):291–6.
17. Bortolatto JF, Pretel H, Floros MC, Luiz ACC, Dantas AAR, Fernandez E, et al. Low Concentration H₂O₂/TiO₂ in Office Bleaching. *J Dent Res.* 2014;93(7 Suppl):66–71.
18. Loguercio AD, Tay LY, Herrera DR, Bauer J, Reis A. Effectiveness of nano-calcium phosphate paste on sensitivity during and after bleaching: a randomized clinical trial. *Braz Oral Res.* 2015;29:1–7.
19. Cartagena AF, Parreiras SO, Loguercio AD, Reis A, Campanha NH. In-office bleaching effects on the pulp flow and tooth sensitivity - case series. *Braz Oral Res.* 2015;29:S1806–83242015000100223.
20. Roderjan DA, Stanislawczuk R, Hebling J, Costa CDS, Reis A, Loguercio AD, et al. Response of Human Pulps to Different In Office Bleaching Techniques: Preliminary Findings. *Braz Dent J.* 2015;26(3):242–8.
21. Mayer-Santos E, Anhesini BH, Shimokawa CAK, Aranha ACC, Eduardo CP, De Freitas P, et al. The potential of low-power laser for reducing dental sensitivity after in-office bleaching: a case report. *Gen Dent.* 2017;65(4):8–11.
22. Moosavi H, Arjmand N, Ahrari F, Zakeri M, Maleknejad F. Effect of low-level laser therapy on tooth sensitivity induced by in-office bleaching. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2016;31(4):713–9.

23. Moosavi H, Maleknejad F, Sharifi M, Ahrari F. A randomized clinical trial of the effect of low-level laser therapy before composite placement on postoperative sensitivity in class V restorations. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2015;30(4):1245–9.
24. de Andrade A, Bossini P, Parizotto N. Use of low level laser therapy to control neuropathic pain: A systematic review. *J Photochemistry Photobiology B: Biology.* 2016;164:36–42.
25. Ramalho KM, De Souza L, Tortamano IP, Adde CA, Rocha RG, Eduardo C, et al. A randomized placebo-blind study of the effect of low power laser on pain caused by irreversible pulpitis. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2016;31(9):1899–905.
26. Yoo YJ, Shon WJ, Baek SH, Kang MK, Kim HC, Lee W, et al. Effect of 1440-Nanometer Neodymium:Yttrium-Aluminum Garnet Laser Irradiation on Pain and Neuropeptide Reduction: A Randomized Prospective Clinical Trial. *J Endod.* 2014;40(1):28–32. doi:10.1016/j.joen.2013.07.011.
27. He WL, Li CJ, Liu ZP, Sun JF, Hu ZA, XYin, et al. Efficacy of lowlevel laser therapy in the management of orthodontic pain: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2013;28(6):1581–9.
28. 28. Gama SKC, Habib FAL, De Carvalho J, Monteiro, Paraguassú GM, Araújo TM, et al. Tooth Movement After Infrared Laser Phototherapy: Clinical Study in Rodents. *Photomed Laser Surg.* 2010;28(Suppl 2):79–83.
29. 29. Pallotta RC, Bjordal JM, Frigo L, Junior ECP, Teixeira S, Marcos RL, et al. Infrared (810-nm) low-level laser therapy on rat experimental knee inflammation. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2012;27(1):71–8.
30. Metin R, Tatli U, Evlice B. Effects of low-level laser therapy on soft and hard tissue healing after endodontic surgery. *Lasers Med Sci.* 2018;33(8):1699–706.
31. 31. Payer M, Jakse N, Pertl C, Truschneegg A, Lechner E, Eskici A, et al. The clinical effect of LLLT in endodontic surgery: a prospective study on 72 cases. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 2005;100(3):375–9.
32. 32. Moreira MS, Diniz IM, Rodrigues MF, De Carvalho R, Carrer FDA, Neves II, et al. In vivo experimental model of orthotopic dental pulp regeneration under the influence of photobiomodulation therapy. *J Photochem Photobiol B.* 2017;166(1):180–6.